

doi:10.5281/zenodo.20006399

Improvisation of Laboratory Reagent (Potassium Carbonate) from Doum Palm (*Hyphaene thebaica*) Leaves and Its Utilization in Titrimetric Analysis for sustainable chemistry and waste-to-wealth initiatives

Yahaya Sara Galo^{1*}, Abubakar Sadiq Galadima¹ and Harira Ibrahim Makinta¹

¹ Department of Chemistry, School of Secondary Education (Sciences), Umar Suleiman College of Education Gashua, Yobe State, Nigeria

***Corresponding Author: Galo Yahaya Sara, Department of Chemistry, School of Secondary Education (Scences) Umar Suleiman College of Education Gashua, Yobe State, Nigeria E-mail: sygalo0066@gmail.com +234 (0) 803 839 7530**

ABSTRACT

Doum palm (*Hyphaene thebaica*) leaves are an abundant agricultural residue in arid and semi-arid regions of Northern Nigeria, yet they remain largely underutilized. In this study, potassium carbonate was prepared from Doum palm (*Hyphaene thebaica*) leaves through controlled combustion and aqueous extraction. The recovered product was characterized using qualitative chemical tests and subsequently applied in acid–base titrimetric analysis. The agricultural waste-derived potassium carbonate appeared as a white, hygroscopic, water-soluble solid with strongly alkaline properties. Titration results showed consistent and reproducible endpoints when reacted with standard hydrochloric acid, indicating that the prepared potassium carbonate is suitable for basic volumetric analysis. The results indicate that potassium carbonate derived from Doum palm (*Hyphaene thebaica*) leaves can serve as a viable alternative to commercial reagents for basic volumetric analysis, particularly in resource-limited laboratories. This study demonstrates the feasibility of converting agricultural waste into valuable laboratory reagents, supporting sustainable chemistry and waste-to-wealth initiatives.

Keywords - Doum palm leaves, *Hyphaene thebaica*, Potassium carbonate, Agricultural waste, Titrimetric analysis, Waste-to-wealth

INTRODUCTION

Agricultural activities generate large quantities of waste materials that are often discarded or poorly managed which often pose significant environmental challenges if not properly managed (Sharma et al., 2024). However, when these wastes are properly managed, it contain valuable inorganic compounds that can be recovered and utilized for industrial and laboratory purposes. This is because, many of these plants residues contain valuable inorganic compounds, particularly potassium that can be recovered and utilized for industrial and laboratory purposes (Samadhi, et al., 2018). This promotes waste-to-wealth, reduces dependence on imported laboratory chemicals and supports sustainable chemistry practices (Okafor 2014).

When agricultural waste such as plant stalks, husks, leaves and palm residues are properly combusted and processed (Babayemi, *et al.*, 2011), potassium carbonate (K₂CO₃), an important laboratory reagent widely used in analytical chemistry, glass manufacturing, soap production (Abah *et al.*, 2019) and food processing can be obtained (Kidwai *et al.*, 2013). Potassium carbonate prepared from agricultural waste can be successfully applied in titrimetric (volumetric) analysis as a basic reagent (Aliyu and Abdullahi 2021)

Potassium present in plant tissues exists mainly as organic and inorganic salts. When organic materials (wood, plants residue etc) are processed under controlled combustion, the organic matter is destroyed, creating ash containing potassium oxide and potassium hydroxide, which react with atmospheric carbon dioxide to form potassium carbonate (Edeoga and Uche 2018):

Potassium carbonate is a white, hygroscopic, water-soluble inorganic salt and can be extracted by leaching the combusted ash with distilled water and the dissolved potassium carbonate is separated from insoluble impurities by filtration and then concentrated by evaporation (Babayemi, *et al.*, 2010; Ningsih *et al.*, 2019).

Potassium carbonate, a moderately strong base widely applied in titrimetric (volumetric) analysis, especially in acid–base titrations (Mendham *et al.*, 2009). Many educational and research laboratories in developing countries like Nigeria rely heavily on imported chemical reagents, which are expensive and sometimes unavailable (Olorunsola 2018). Meanwhile, potassium-rich agricultural wastes such as Doum palm (*Hyphaene thebaica*) leaves are discarded without utilization (Aliyu and Abdullahi 2021). The lack of local reagent production contributes to high laboratory costs and environmental pollution (Sharma *et al.*, 2024). Preparation of potassium carbonate from locally available agricultural waste like Doum palm (*Hyphaene thebaica*) leaves offers a sustainable and cost-effective alternative (Eze and Okeke 2021).

Doum palm (*Hyphaene thebaica*) is a drought-resistant branching palm tree native to Africa and the Middle East. It thrives in arid and semi-arid regions of Northern Nigeria, particularly in Gashua, Bade Local Government area of Yobe State. The leaves are widely used for local crafts, while the residues are usually discarded as waste and underutilized. These leaves are fibrous, tough and rich in mineral content, especially potassium salts, making them suitable for alkali extraction (Oyeleke and Oyewole 2011). While the fruit and trunk have economic uses, the leaves are often discarded after traditional applications, generating substantial waste. These leaves are rich in potassium salts, which upon combustion can yield potassium carbonate (K₂CO₃), an important alkali used in chemical laboratories (Adefila and Abdullahi 2019). Several studies have shown that agricultural waste such as plantain peels, cocoa pod husks and palm wastes are rich in alkali metals, especially potassium (Babayemi, *et al.*, 2010). These wastes can be converted into valuable laboratory reagents through controlled combustion and extraction (Aliyu and Abdullahi 2021). Potassium carbonate was reported to have been successfully extracted from *Pennisetum Glaucum* (Millet) Straw an agricultural waste for domestic and industrial applications (Bala *et al.*, 2024). Similarly, potassium carbonate was extracted from empty fruit bunch palm ash and was effectively used in the laboratory as base catalyst for biodiesel making (Yitnowati, *et al.*, 2008). This study therefore explores the improvisation of potassium carbonate from Doum palm (*Hyphaene thebaica*) leaves through combustion and aqueous extraction and its characterization using simple qualitative tests. This study also applied the improvised potassium carbonate in acid–base titrimetric analysis and compare the performance of the improvised reagent with standard laboratory potassium carbonate. Producing potassium carbonate locally from Doum palm (*Hyphaene thebaica*) leaves through combustion and aqueous extraction and its characterization promotes waste-to-wealth, reduces dependence on imported potassium carbonate, control environmental pollution (Sharma *et al.*, 2024) and supports sustainable chemistry practices (Olorunsola 2018). Potassium carbonate prepared from Doum palm (*Hyphaene thebaica*) leaves can be successfully applied in titrimetric (volumetric) analysis as a basic reagent (Usman and Mohammed 2022; Suleiman 2020).

Titrimetric analysis is a quantitative analytical technique based on volume measurement (Mendham *et al.*, 2009). Potassium carbonate is commonly used in acid–base titrations due to its predictable stoichiometric reaction with strong acids.

Properties of Potassium carbonate

IUPAC Name	Potassium Trioxocarbonate(IV)
Chemical formula	K ₂ CO ₃
Density	2.43 g/cm ³
Molecular weight	138.205 g/mol
Melting Point	891 °C
Boiling Point	Decomposes
State	Solid

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Area

The study was conducted in Gashua, the headquarters of Bade Local Government Area in Yobe State, Northeastern Nigeria. Gashua lies between latitude 12°52'N and longitude 11°02'E. Situated in the Northeastern part of Nigeria, Gashua has an area of 3,336 square kilometer and population of 125,817 as at (2006 census) and is positioned on the banks of the Kumadugu Yobe River. The town is characterized by a semi-arid climate (Sahel savanna region) featuring hot, dry seasons and a short rainy season (June–September) with sparse vegetation dominated by drought-resistant plants such as the Doum Palm and thorny shrubs. The community engages in agriculture, date palm cultivation and small-scale processing of local resources. The availability of Doum palm leaves and agricultural residues makes Gashua a suitable location for this study.

Fig 1: Study Area

Source: Department of Geography, GIS unit, Umar Suleiman College of Education, Gashua (2026)

Collection and Preparation of Leaves

Fresh Doum Palm (*Hyphaene thebaica*) leaves were collected from a farmland in Gashu'a town of Bade Local Government Area of Yobe State, Nigeria. The leaves were transported to the Department of Chemistry, Umar Suleiman College of Education, Gashu'a, cleaned, cut into small pieces, air-dried thoroughly for two (2) weeks and then oven-dried at 105 °C to remove moisture. About 50kg, which is 50,000g of the dried Doum Palm (*Hyphaene thebaica*) leaves was burnt in a crucible at 550 – 600°C for 3 hours to obtain grayish ash. The ash was sieved to remove impurities and then transferred and placed into a clay pot which have previously been perforated with several small holes at the bottom and rested on top of plastic container which serves as receiver (Obi et al., 2017). 10,000cm³ of distilled water was then be poured freely on top of the ash to cover the entire surface and gently percolates through the ash until drops of the extract was seen dripping into the receiver. The filtrate was then evaporated gently to dryness over low heat in an evaporating dish, leaving a solid white crystalline residue (crude potassium carbonate) (Oyeleke and Oyewole 2011). The obtained substance was dried in a desiccator, weighed and stored in an airtight container due to its hygroscopic nature. The crystalline potassium carbonate was characterized by subjecting it to solubility test, pH determination, flame test and reaction with an acid (Obi et al., 2017).

Titrimetric Analysis

A known concentration of the prepared potassium carbonate solution (a weak base) was titrated against standard hydrochloric acid solution using methyl orange as an indicator. The neutralization reaction proceeded accordingly:

Reaction

Experimental Procedure

- i. A known mass of the prepared K₂CO₃ from the Doum Palm (*Hyphaene thebaica*) leave was dissolved in distilled water.
- ii. 25 cm³ of the solution was pipetted and transferred into a conical flask.
- iii. 2 – 3 drops of methyl orange was added to the solution in the conical flask to serve as an indicator.
- iv. The solution was titrated with a standard solution of hydrochloric acid.
- v. The endpoint was indicated by a color change from yellow to orange.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1:- Physical Observation of the Improvised Potassium Carbonate

Property	Observation
Appearance	White solid
Solubility Test	Highly soluble in water
pH Test	Strongly alkaline (pH ≈ 11)
Hygroscopic nature	Absorbs moisture

Source: Laboratory Analysis, 2026

Table 2:- Qualitative Test Results

Test	Observation	Inference
Flame Test	Lilac flame	Potassium present
Reaction with Acid	Effervescence	Carbonate confirmed

Source: Laboratory Analysis, 2026

Table 3:- Titration Reading Result

Burette Reading (cm ³)	Rough	First	Second	Third
Final Burette Reading (cm ³)	17.70	17.50	17.60	17.55
Initial Burette Reading (cm ³)	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Volume of Acid Used (cm ³)	17.70	17.50	17.60	17.55

Source: Laboratory Analysis, 2026

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Average titre value} &= \frac{17.50 + 17.60 + 17.55}{3} \\ &= \frac{4952.65.90}{3} \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Average titre value} = 17.55 \text{ cm}^3$$

The concentration of the improvised potassium carbonate was calculated from the following expression:

$$\frac{M_a V_a}{M_b V_b} = \frac{\Pi_a}{\Pi_b}$$

Where,

M_a = Molar concentration of acid

V_a = Volume of acid used

M_b = Molar concentration of base

V_b = Volume of base used

Π_a = Number of moles of acid

Π_b = Number of moles of base

The results obtained from the study confirm the successful preparation of potassium carbonate from Doum palm (*Hyphaene thebaica*) leaves. This shows that Doum palm (*Hyphaene thebaica*) leaves are a viable agricultural waste source for the improvisation of potassium carbonate. From table 1, the white, hygroscopic and water-soluble nature of the improvised product is consistent with the known physical properties of potassium carbonate as reported in standard chemical literature (Vogel, 2000; Mendham *et al.*, 2009). The strong alkaline pH seen in the improvised potassium carbonate, indicates the presence of carbonate ions, which align with earlier works that extracted Alkali from Agricultural waste (Oyeleke and Oyewole 2011), and reported that plant ashes rich in potassium typically yield alkaline carbonate salts after aqueous extraction. The qualitative test results (table 2) confirmed the presence of potassium and carbonate ions. These properties are consistent with standard potassium carbonate as reported in standard chemical literature (Vogel, 2000; Mendham *et al.*, 2009). The hygroscopic nature of the product further

supports its identification as potassium carbonate, since K_2CO_3 readily absorbs moisture from the atmosphere (Skoog *et al.*, 2014). These findings also align with earlier works that extracted potassium carbonate from plant ashes (Abah *et al.*, 2019; Okeke and Okeke 2016; Owoeye *et al.*, 2020). The qualitative flame test result (table 2) produced a characteristic lilac coloration, confirming the presence of potassium ions. This observation equally aligns with standard qualitative inorganic analysis procedure, where potassium salts exhibit a lilac or violet flame due to electronic excitation of potassium atoms (Harvey, 2016). The effervescence seen upon reacting it with dilute hydrochloric acid in table 2 confirms the presence of carbonate ions, as carbon dioxide gas is liberated during acid-carbonate reactions (Vogel, 2000).

Table 4 shows that the potassium carbonate yield was approximately 16.55% by mass of ash obtained and upon titration with hydrochloric acid, the results in table 3 showed consistent titre values across replicate trials indicating that the improvised potassium carbonate reacted stoichiometrically with hydrochloric acid, following the expected reaction pathway. The reproducibility and reliable stoichiometric behavior of the agricultural waste-derived potassium carbonate demonstrate that it can serve effectively in acid-base titrations and the results are comparable with those obtained using commercially available potassium carbonate. Although, minor impurities may still be present in the sample due to co-extracted inorganic salts (sodium and calcium compounds), which are commonly found in plant ashes. However, the impurities did not significantly affect the titration accuracy (Okafor, 2014), which is likely attributed to the fact that acid-base titrimetric analysis is relatively tolerant of minor inorganic contaminants, especially when methyl orange is used as the indicator (Mendham *et al.*, 2009). Despite being locally prepared, the reproducibility of the titre value suggests that, the improvised potassium carbonate possessed sufficient purity and stability for basic volumetric analysis. This align with the work of Adejumo and Ola (2010), who reported that alkali compounds derived from agricultural waste can perform comparably to commercial reagents in teaching laboratories.

The findings of this study demonstrate that Doum palm (*Hyphaene thebaica*) leaves, an agricultural waste, can be transformed into useful laboratory reagents – potassium carbonate and support the concept of waste-to-wealth, where agricultural waste-derived reagents is applied in teaching and routine analytical laboratories. This approach not only reduces environmental waste but also lowers the cost of laboratory chemicals, particularly in resource-limited educational institutions (FAO, 2017).

Table 4:- Extraction of Potassium Carbonate from ash of Doum Palm (*Hyphaene thebaica*) leaves

Weight of Leaf (g)	Weight of Ash Obtained (g)	Weight of crude K_2CO_3 Obtained (g)	Percentage of crude K_2CO_3 in Ash (%)
50,000	3,800	629	16.55

Source: Laboratory Analysis, 2026

$$\text{Percentage of } K_2CO_3 = \frac{\text{Weight of } K_2CO_3 \text{ Obtained (g)}}{\text{Weight of Ash obtained (g)}} \times 100$$

CONCLUSION

The study successfully demonstrated the improvisation of potassium carbonate from Doum Palm (Goruba) leaves collected in Gashua, Bade Local Government Area of Yobe State using a simple local techniques. The process—ashing, extraction, filtration and crystallization—yielded a reagent whose chemical characteristics matches that of standard potassium carbonate and found to be suitable for titrimetric analysis, particularly in acid-base titrations. The procedure is cost-effective, environmentally friendly and suitable for low-resource laboratory settings. Although purity levels may vary compared to commercial reagents, the improvised potassium carbonate remains a valuable alternative for sustainable laboratory practices and demonstrates the practical value of agricultural waste in educational and experimental applications.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Further purification should be carried out for analytical-grade applications.
2. Similar studies should be conducted using other agricultural wastes.
3. Local production of laboratory reagents should be encouraged in schools.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

Authors are grateful to Tertiary Education Trust Fund, Abuja Nigeria for an intervention fund for this research work and to the Managements of Umar Suleiman College of Education Gashua for their support. Appreciation is also extended to the Department of Chemistry Education for granting us access to the laboratory facility for the work.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest.

Authors' contributions

This work was carried out in collaboration between all authors. Author YSG designed the study, wrote the protocol, wrote the first draft of the manuscript. Authors YSG and ASG carried out all laboratory work, analysis of the study. Authors ASG and HIM managed the literature searches and edited the manuscript. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

REFERENCES

- Abah, J., Ogbodo, S. O., & Umar, A. (2019). Production of potash from selected agricultural wastes and its application in soap making. *Journal of Chemical Society of Nigeria*, 44(1), 77–84.
- Adefila, S. S., & Abdullahi, M. (2019). Improvisation of laboratory materials for effective teaching of chemistry in secondary schools. *Journal of Science Education*, 7(2), 45–52.
- Adejumo, O., & Bamiro, O. M. (2015). Assessment of potash from agricultural residues in Nigeria. *International Journal of Innovative Science and Research Technology*, 2(5), 32–38.
- Aliyu, M. D., & Abdullahi, U. (2021). Utilization of local resources for laboratory reagent improvisation in Nigerian schools. *Nigerian Journal of Science Education*, 18(3), 45–52.
- Anastas, P. T., & Warner, J. C. (1998). *Green Chemistry: Theory and Practice*. Oxford University Press.
- Babayemi, J. O., Adewuyi, G. O., and Obi-gbedi, N. O. (2011). Evaluation of Options in Wood Waste Management: Burning and Consequent Alkali Production. *Journal of Sustainable Development and Environmental Protection*. 1(2): 99-108.
- Babayemi, J.O., Duada, K.T., Nwude, D.O., and Kayode, A. A. (2010). Evaluation of the Composition and Chemistry of Ash and Potash from Various Plant Materials. A Review, *Journal of Applied sciences* 10(16):1820-1824.
- Bala. A. T., Iliya. I. N and Halima N 2024. Extraction and Characterization of Potassium Carbonate from *Pennisetum Glaucum* (Millet) Straw for Domestic and Industrial Applications *ChemClass Journal* Vol. 9 Issue 1 (2024); 136-148
- Edeoga, H. O., & Uche, L. N. (2018). Ash composition of selected tropical plant leaves and their industrial relevance. *African Journal of Pure and Applied Chemistry*, 12(4), 56–62.
- Eze, C. U., & Okeke, P. N. (2021). Local improvisation of laboratory reagents and apparatus in science teaching. *African Journal of Education and Technology*, 11(1), 23–30.
- FAO. (2017). *Non-wood forest products of Africa*. Food and Agriculture Organization.
- Greenwood, N. N., & Earnshaw, A. (2012). *Chemistry of the Elements* (2nd ed.). Butterworth-Heinemann.
- Mendham, J., Denney, R. C., Barnes, J. D., & Thomas, M. (2009). *Vogel's Quantitative Chemical Analysis*. Pearson.
- Mendham, J., Denney, R. C., Barnes, J. D., & Thomas, M. (2009). *Vogel's Textbook of Quantitative Chemical Analysis*. Prentice Hall.

- Ningsih, L.M. et al. 2019. Leaching of Potassium from Oil Palm Empty Fruit Bunch (OPEFB) Using Tapioca Wastewater. Proceedings of the International Conference on Sustainable Biomass (ICSB 2019), 202: 281–286.
- NPC (2006). Population Census of the Federal Republic of Nigeria. National Population Commission retrieved from www.population.gov.ng
- Obi, C. C., Eze, S. O., & Okwu, D. E. (2017). Extraction and characterization of potash from plant materials. *International Journal of Scientific and Engineering Research*, 8(6), 1245–1251.
- Okafor, J. C. (2014). Waste-to-wealth potentials of agro-residues. *African Journal of Environmental Science*, 8(2), 45–52.
- Okeke, E. O., & Okeke, C. A. (2016). Production of potash from plantain and banana peels for soap making. *Nigerian Journal of Chemical Research*, 21(1), 56–62.
- Olorunsola, E. O. (2018). Improvised materials in science laboratories: A sustainable approach in developing countries. *International Journal of Innovative Research in Education*, 5(3), 54–61.
- Owoeye, T. F., Omodara, O. J., & Olaleye, O. O. (2020). Comparative study of potash produced from agricultural waste materials. *Journal of Applied Science and Environmental Management*, 24(2), 243–248.
- Oyeleke, S. B., & Oyewole, O. A. (2011). Alkali production from agricultural wastes. *Journal of Applied Sciences Research*, 7(3), 234–239.
- Samadhi, T. W., Narcia, F. dan Amril, H. 2018. Preliminary Evaluation of Potassium Extraction from Bamboo Ash. MATEC Web of Conferences, 156: 1–4.
- Sharma P et al., (2024) Sustainable organic waste management and future directions for environmental protection and techno-economic perspectives. *Current Pollution Reports*. 2024;10(3):1-19
- Skoog, D. A., Holler, F. J., & Crouch, S. R. (2014). *Fundamentals of Analytical Chemistry*. Cengage Learning.
- Suleiman, A. M. (2020). Utilization of locally sourced materials for laboratory reagent production. *Nigerian Journal of Applied Sciences*, 9(4), 78–86.
- Usman, S., & Mohammed, A. (2022). Local resource utilization in chemical education: A case for sustainable reagent improvisation. *Journal of Science and Technology Education*, 11(2), 101–109.
- Vogel, A. I. (2000). *Textbook of Quantitative Chemical Analysis* (6th ed.). Pearson Education.
- Yitnowati, U., Yoeswono, Wahyuningsih, T.D., dan Tahir, I. 2008. The Use of Empty Fruit Bunch Palm Ash as Source of Base Catalyst (K₂CO₃) for Biodiesel Making from Castor Oil (*Ricinus communis*). Seminar Nasional Kimia XVIII(November).Jurnal Teknik Kimia, Vol. 30, No. 1, 2024 Page | 79